

The Generalized Theory of Swing: An Interview with Malcolm Braff

Conducted by Patrick Huss

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Abstract

In this interview, Malcolm Braff discusses the Generalized Theory of Swing (GTS) — a framework developed over twenty years describing rhythmic phrasing as a continuous and functionally structured parameter applicable to any metric subdivision. Topics include: the wave nature of musical time; swing as tempering in the rhythmic domain; harmonicity as synchronicity; groove balance and phrasing direction; the extension of swing to odd subdivisions; morphing between meters; the computational and mathematical directions of the research (vector spaces, Euclidean rhythms, Quplets); and the meaning of music as the art of connecting. The interview was conducted by Patrick Huss as part of his master's thesis research.

Keywords: swing, microrhythm, groove, phrasing, tempering, General Theory of Rhythm, musical time, improvisation, rhythm theory, Quplets

What is swing?

P: Thank you for being here, Malcolm!

M: Pleasure, thank you for the invitation!

P: My first question is: Could you describe your definition of what swing is for you? An easy one to start with.

M: The short version or the long version?

P: You can take as much time as you want.

M: Actually, I really never asked myself that precise question — like what it is for me. I have tried to describe the functionality of it and many, many things about it — the different qualities of swing — but what it is exactly... Probably the best personal definition I can give to it: swing is what reflects the wave quality of time. It is what reflects a time that functions with pulses, and so it is a time that has a wave shape — a time that's bouncing. So swing is intimately connected to what time is. Maybe not time in general — that's a more philosophical question — but at least what musical time is for me.

P: So you would say that it's a wave in opposition to a particle?

M: No, not particle — but more like — of course there's this funny parallel we can draw with the wave quality of light or of time — so it's as opposed to a linear time. A time that would be linear, constant. So for me musical time has nothing of that. Actually, it is the time perception and the reality of musical time is successive states of expansion and compression of time. So yes, we can relate it to physics and Einstein's relativity etc., but the experience of the time flow as a musician is nothing linear, actually.

P: And how would you describe the musical phrasing that takes place to kind of establish this?

M: Well, I think it's something very basic — it's phrasing as we know it in the Western music tradition. We do have this notion of a time that is something that can be expressive, that is made of — we describe it as durations rather than events. And so the event-based description of rhythm comes from the notation, comes from the study of rhythm as we know it. But I think the practice of music — you know that sound has an envelope, has a duration — and so time in music is not strictly an event-based phenomenon. And so I think swing also, if not considered from the event perspective — swing is not a displacement of events over a linear timeline, swinging is really this continuum of time that is bouncing, pressing and expanding as I said before. So I believe, if we look really at the whole tradition of what music expression is about, and how it actually happens over the duration of the musical expression, then this notion of a continuum of time is something that we very much know about. Maybe less as rhythm or percussion players — sometimes we forget about it. But you have a horn player or a singer — it's really obvious that there is a presence to what's happening, that is a continuum, an unbroken and uninterrupted phenomenal perception. So swing for me is to put rhythm into that perspective.

P: So it's directly related to movement, you would say?

M: Yeah, obviously. If you look at how the music tradition is transmitted, the oral part of our musical transmission is made with gestures: we express it through movement because then it's obvious, we can really relate to it. So I believe that if not movement-based per essence — which is something I do believe — but even without going there, movement can express that quality. It's the best thing to express that, to illustrate that, to suggest from that. So yeah, very much movement-based, yes.

P: I was just thinking: because you were talking about the importance of that ongoing thing, and movement for me is something that's moving — it's not stopping, it's ongoing.

M: Exactly. When we hit drums, or whatever movement I have to produce a musical event, that movement is not just a clock signal. It's not. It has anticipation. So it's a whole movement that leads to the moment of the production of the sound. And it's not like I'm here and then suddenly I'm there producing the sound. There's a whole continuum of movement. And of course this is not local — it's not yes or no. You go between states of yes and no. The muscles have this contraction and release movement, it alternates between those states, but it doesn't alternate like a square wave — it's more of a sine wave that goes from one state to the other.

What does swing do? The groove effect

P: You were talking about in the beginning that you hadn't really defined what swing is for you, but that you've developed or found things that it does, basically — how it functions and what effects it has on the groove perception or the music itself. Can you go into that a little bit?

M: Yes, I can maybe restate the idea that I'd never questioned — what swing is to me. I did question what swing does to me. But maybe a more deep philosophical question about what swing means is something that I would be inclined to start asking myself. I find this interesting.

M: But then what it does to me on different levels: I think to start with, it really emphasizes the pulse feel. In many ways. But one of them is that this pulsatory, waving perception of time — the cycle of that wave is actually the pulse. So it strengthens the pulse feel in my own perception. But also it makes the pulse objective. It makes the pulse obvious, unavoidable so to speak. Because regardless of the musical text that is expressed, the substrate in which that text takes place — the meter or the rhythmical grid — is happening in waves that are cyclic and that you can identify through swing.

M: So if I have a regular waveform happening, I can identify the frequency of that cycle but I'm not able to state which fundamental it is the harmonic of. If I have a certain rate that is regular, quantized, clock — and that rate, especially in the subdivision domain — we have in psychoacoustics a limited range of perception of a pulse that is really a pulse we can dance to. Maybe it's linked to the limitations of the body — we cannot dance at 500 BPM for real. We will have to really group those fast pulses in order to audiate a much slower pulse that our body can dance to.

M: So if I hear that rate that is regular, fast enough to not be a pulse but to be a subdivision of the pulse, I cannot state — unless there are some cultural elements like a kick on the downbeat, or a melody that really obviously points at how the pulse is organized — I'm not able to say. From the clock itself I'm not able to say: okay, is this a triplet subdivision of the pulse or is this a four-subdivision? Sixteenth notes to a quarter-note pulse, or are those eighth notes? Or even five-tuplets? I'm not able, just from the 'ta-ta-ta-ta-ta-ta' to say: okay, where is the pulse?

M: But if it's swinging, then there is a cycle embedded in this subdivision that points at the pulse with no possible avoiding. And this is why it also makes the pulse cycle recognizable — that you can identify it. I often say: okay, if an alien comes and listens to music and this alien is not able to distinguish between pitches etc. — it's just able to recognize when events take place. Then if it's not swinging, this alien is not able to identify the pulse cycle, only the sub-pulse, only the subdivision will be identified. But then you lose — it's like you're playing an E pitch and if you're not given the context to tell you that this E pitch is actually the major third of a C major chord, if you don't hear the bass, if this is out of context, then all you hear is an E, but not the function of a major third. So you don't hear the ground, the tonality — which

would be the pulse in that case, the C.

M: So, if my E is swinging then I hear the C. And one can make this experiment with electronics: you have a regular pulse that you fix to a frequency like the E, and of course you don't hear any C in there if it's a pure sine wave — no harmonics. And as soon as you start swinging that sine wave, then immediately — if you swing it to a cycle that would be the E, so if you swing it in groups of five — then it's obvious: you hear that this five is actually a five, that this five is actually the fifth harmonic of a much lower pitch. So really just by swinging this sine wave in groups of five, you audiate the C frequency immediately. So that's another reason. Those two reasons why it emphasizes the pulse feel and makes the pulse cycle recognizable — that you can identify it.

P: While we are on this topic of making it recognizable — maybe we can talk a little bit about the odd meter topic: how swing is effective to practice odd meters or to make them clear for a musician or a listener so that they are not just in the air or conceptual but really embodied.

M: Exactly — if you apply swing to an odd subdivision, then you hear that cycle of that odd subdivision as a real cycle. Maybe if someone is not used to doing that, it would take a while to get into that practice, but not too long from my experience. The advantage is that immediately you start audiating for real that pulse cycle that is maybe subdivided in five — to perform a five-eight and avoid the temptation, because of our habits, to actually audiate it in maybe five-four with a middle-bar syncopation, or even five-two sometimes. So if you really want to feel that cycle of the five-eight, just making these five groups swing — because you're distributing longs and shorts — makes that cycle really obvious. And I have experienced that it's a good way to approach odd meters if one has difficulties with, say, a short seven or a short five — just introducing the swing concept, all of a sudden you can really hear it.

Swing as tempering — the rhythmic analogue of equal temperament

P: So maybe you could talk a little bit about the similarities of the rhythmic and pitch domain, this phenomenon of tempering. This also probably goes under the effects of swing. Maybe you could address this in a more general way.

M: So yeah, this is another property that swinging — for example the odd meter — has. It's that swing can be looked at as a bridge or a connector between one subdivision and the other. We often say: okay, jazz swing is between the two and the three subdivision. It's not precisely a triplet feel but it's of course not straight eighths — it's there somewhere in between. And this already states that it's in between the two and the three subdivision. It is a bridge, it's a connector between those two. In many ways.

M: As a connector, as something that's in between, jazz swing — a good nice in-between swing — can be audiated, forcing your ears a bit, as a triplet feel if you want, or can be audiated as straight eighths. So the listener and even more the improviser has the choice to relate to that swing from the two-subdivision perspective or from the three-triplet perspective.

You have Cannonball — he's very tripletish — and in the same band you will have Miles Davis, who is really more to the straight eighth. So this means that this place where swing resides is an ambiguous place. It has both perspectives, it connects them together but it gives also the possibility to actually look at it from one perspective or the other.

M: And in that respect, it's very similar to the well-tempered clavier where we have twelve tones but we have much more functions than just twelve tones. So we have D-sharp and E-flat, but it's that one key. And we could even have F double-flat. How tempering in the pitch domain works is that I have on the piano this dark key that's there, that I can play in both contexts — if I need a D-sharp or E-flat or even F double-flat. The actual pitch that's there is really in between the D-sharp and the E-flat, somewhere in between. As a singer or a horn player — and certainly a violin player — you're not really having the same position if you're playing a D-sharp or an E-flat. And even on the piano, which is this tempered thing, if I'm really playing B major or C minor, that D-sharp/E-flat pitch is not going to be the same — I will pitch-intonate it to really reflect the functionality of the major third, etc.

M: So this position that the dark key on the piano has — this in-between position — is close enough to the expected D-sharp and close enough to the expected E-flat so that our brain tolerates it as consonant, as the expected pitch. But of course, if you're in just intonation and then you play that key, it will not work — it will really clash with the expected harmonic identity. It's going to be out of tune. But that position that's really in between has this tolerance — it's close enough to the expected pitch, whichever pitch is expected, so that it fits in that pocket.

M: And so swing plays a very similar role. The jazz swing can take in the triplet feel as well as the two subdivision. Functionally speaking, it will be consonant, harmonious — it will fulfill the function we expect from it in both cases. So yes, for me swing also has this tempering property, but in the rhythm domain.

P: *So you would say this pitch discrepancy — if we transfer it to the rhythmic domain — is something that our ear accepts like a flam, something rhythmic?*

M: Yeah, exactly.

P: *So if it's close enough. When it's getting too large then it's two events and then it's not one thing anymore.*

M: I don't know too precisely about psychoacoustics but of course we have something similar depending on where you are in the range of perception in the pitch domain. Too low, you don't hear. It changes your perception of what's a true harmonic, a true function or what's not. So that whole functional perception is really dependent on the speed. So of course that flam — if I slow it down extremely — one year later the other one: that will not be perceived by the brain as a synchronous, synced event. There's a limit to that perception. The absolute distance between the two events, the time interval, will be taken as something accepted as synchronous only within a certain range of perception. So yes, the neighbouring of the

expected accent or the expected pitch plays an essential role in this tempering effect.

Long and short — extending swing beyond the duplet

P: And so — let's call it the jazz swing — it can be between the eighth note and the triplet. But maybe it would be good to talk about what this observation means for other groups of notes except for the two notes we have in jazz swing, or what other kinds of swing can be observed in the world or created with this observation.

M: Well to start with, the swing itself — some scholars have described it as: okay, no, it's actually a five, so the correct way of swinging is having the three-to-two, long/short. So whenever you swing, if you want to really swing correctly, you have to subdivide the whole thing in five and play this three-two thing — this is where it's supposed to be. And we could go further right, we could say four-to-three or five-to-three.

M: Well, that's the first thing: the same way when you're swinging it has the functionality of being a two-subdivision — you imagine it, perform it as a two-subdivision (one and two and three and four and). Very rarely would someone effectively be in the five-tuplet subdivision. But this would be possible of course if it's not too fast, etc. So the same way we can audiate it as a three, we can audiate it as a five, and as a seven and whatever.

M: And that's one beauty of being in between and especially in between the two-to-one ratio. If you're in between the long and the short — between the straight eighth note and the triplet feel, if applied to jazz swing — already to the straight two or to the straight three you're having this tempering effect, where it's close enough so that your brain accepts it as being a two or being a three. And because if you go higher in the subdivision you make it even closer to the expected five or to the expected seven or whatever. So you are in this — maybe we can call it the gray zone — where actually all subdivisions are possible and will sound harmonious, all subdivisions of the actual pulse. So you actually have all of a sudden a rich timbre of the pulse, where before you would have only the one harmonic. You would have the pulse but only the octave or the fifth — a poor sound in terms of overtones, of harmonics, so timbre. But as soon as you swing, you have this very rich pulse in terms of possible harmonics that fit in, and you really audiate them. And to do the experiment with electronics is very nice because indeed you not only hear one overtone pitch — all of a sudden you have many, many pitches, a rich timbre that appears there.

M: So this is one thing. And the other thing is of course that if you apply this long-short distribution with other subdivisions than the two-subdivision that we're used to when it comes to swing, well, you have that same phenomenon: the richness of timbre and the richness of consonant other ratios or other subdivisions that would fit in what you're doing, but with higher subdivisions. Some people know about the West African triplet or the Brazilian sixteenth — known examples of things that people call swing. Brazilians call their phrased sixteenth note swing, although it's not two-note swing — it's a four-note swing. But besides those examples that not everybody in the academic world — I'm talking about jazz schools —

knows about, of course if we apply this swing to a five-tuplet, swinging our fast five-eight, then you have a similar phenomenon. You have a five but that's totally harmonious — even entering this gray zone — to actually any other subdivision. So it allows... the fanciest thing that people consider when looking at this is that it allows those quite challenging ratios. I'm able to play not only 7 over 5 but 11 over 5, or 13, and all ratios.

M: Well, speaking of — it goes back to the tempering. The main advantage of the well-tempered clavier is that every pitch in the scale — all twelve pitches — has multiple possible functions to each and every other element of this scale, which in just intonation is not possible because then you have a root and every other pitch has a reason to be, a meaning of life, that is strictly related to that original pitch which is the fundamental. And in the well-tempered, each and every pitch has a harmonic function to each and every other pitch — and not only one, sometimes even many. So you have this pitch that can be the minor third or the sharp nine, things like that.

M: So as you swing and you enter into this richness of timbre — where actually all different ratios will sound consonant in terms of functionality relative to your swinging subdivision — it has a similar effect. So the tempering gets there also. By swinging the subdivisions and having different possible swings, you slowly get into a general perception of all those subdivisions that are relative to each other in a functional way. So this is the first thing that normally people are attracted to when exposed to this approach: 'Oh wow, I can perform 17 over 9, that's so cool!'

M: But there is this hidden gem for me really — the golden dust in the center — that is about not performing in ratios but this quality of time that it brings. A phrased five-tuplet helps me audiate that cycle of five on the one hand but also, through its timbre — depending on which swing you chose, meaning how you distribute your longs and shorts — it will have a certain color, even Klangfarbe — we could make this parallel. And that's really something that has for me opened a new universe of perceptions: there are so many different fives even at the same tempo, and each of them has its very specific and unique taste and color. Of course it's super cool that it enables me to play 11 over that five and whatever, but more so it's really the beauty of the different colors. So really it's been for me like stepping out of a colorblind world into all of a sudden discovering all the colors of nature, all the flowers. You get out of the black and white perception and wow, it's so rich — and then it's of course a parameter of expression.

Morphing — rhythm as timbre modulation

P: What I was just thinking also, is that this enrichment and the functionality also enables the transition between different subdivisions or pulses — like a different form of modulation, but in the rhythmic domain, a gradual movement like what you call morphing. Maybe you could talk about this.

M: Yeah, that's also a fancy thing: morphing. Morphing can be compared to modulating the timbre of your instrument. If you play an instrument where you have to sustain the sound — not like the piano where when you play it the envelope of the sound, the timbre, is given — or through electronics with modulating filters and things. This rhythm morphing for me feels a bit similar to that. It's actually changing the timbre of the pulse. And of course there are many things that have been done in spectral music and even more with microtonality now, where you can alter the timbre of your sound so that an overtone is brought up and it's almost like having this pitch that you can now relate to and do a harmonic modulation in that direction.

M: So something similar happens in the pulse domain with morphing. If you're able to modulate the amount of swing and modulate the type of swing that you're applying to your subdivision, then you get into this multifunctionality where you can indeed make a rhythm glissando or a rhythm crossfade — I don't know how to say that — but where indeed the rhythms are morphing from one color, one timbre, to another and then having a rhythm modulation. And it's somehow an extension of this idea of multifunctionality — the same way it enables me to play 11 over 5 or whatever, it will then enable me to proceed to a rhythm modulation based on the 11 over 5 tuplet rather than the triplet. So yes, it opens the door to more complex, ratio-wise rhythm modulations.

Groove balance — the gravity of the pulse

***P:** What I was just thinking about is also what you were calling the timbre of the pulse — discovering this richness. The one aspect of this, the different timbres of the pulse, is also this gravity aspect. You have these terms in common musicians' language like a laid-back feeling or something that the pulse feels rushed. Maybe you can shortly talk about this balance of gravity of the pulse.*

M: If I describe it in terms of math or physics: I have the pulse cycle and if the subdivision is evenly distributed — not even in terms of even versus odd, but really evenly distributed — the energy available throughout the pulse cycle is balanced in that there is as much energy towards the next pulse as towards the previous one. So if I subdivide the pulse cycle in two parts, one part being the first half and the other part being the second half in terms of closeness to a pulse moment — after the first half of the pulse cycle I am closer to the next pulse than I am to the previous one, and vice versa. So an evenly distributed subdivision system, if you sum all the events, will have as much energy towards the next pulse as towards the previous one. It would be well balanced.

M: But if you swing, you might actually displace energy towards one side or the other. If there's more energy available closer to the next pulse, I call this a positive groove balance; if you have more energy closer to the previous pulse, then this is a negative groove balance. And my observation is that this reflects pretty well this feeling of laid-back or drive. Something is laid-back because it has more energy towards the pulse that just occurred than it has to the next one.

M: And so how I represent this to myself: when something has a positive groove balance, the way I audiate how events are connected, how they come together in one phrase — I'll be considering the pulse moment as a destination. Things are closer to that moment. Rhythmically speaking, the events are calling for the pulse, the phrase lands on the pulse. So the pulse moment is a landing point, something you aim at — as opposed to being a moment from which everything echoes or unfolds. That will be more the laid-back or negative groove balance.

P: *So it's not something with the pulse itself changing but more the waveform?*

M: Yeah, exactly. If I translate that into that wave perception of time — different grooving pulses will correspond to different wave forms, wave shapes. It all has the same pulse cycle but it's bouncing more like this or more like that. And so it's not displacement of the beat — laid-back for me is definitely not displacement of the beat, because the beat is the root. How can I displace the beat?

M: I indeed can keep a pitch and change the root. If I have the E example again — I have a C root that makes it the major third — I can slightly pitch my E so that it gets slightly out of tune one way or the other. And I could achieve the same thing to the root to suggest the same effect. But as long as the root remains the root, functionally speaking, my ear will adapt — it's the E that will sound out of tune. If I have this interval, a 10th, the major third and the root, and the interval is a bit short, it's never the root that's going to sound out of tune — it is the harmonic. And so for me it's the same rhythmically speaking. It cannot be that the beat is displaced. The beat is your root note, your fundamental. So it's really: the moment of the pulse is always the moment of the pulse. What is modulated, what is altered, is how it bounces — the shape of time in between those pulse moments.

P: *Yeah, thank you. I think we could talk about this topic for a few more days.*

M: Yeah, yeah, absolutely.

P: *Which we will hopefully do without the cameras. But of course I would like to change the subject a little bit. There is also this whole computational and mathematical part of this thing that I'm also quite interested in because of my small background in mathematics. Maybe you can talk a little bit about what you did on this front. I know that there's this plugin for Macs. And what are your recent discoveries in that domain?*

Computational and mathematical research directions

M: I am interested in bringing it to electronics in different ways for two reasons: one of them is to have computer-based music featuring that approach for performance, teaching, and experimenting. But also I'm interested more fundamentally in trying to discover what's the behavior of this in terms of physics, mathematically speaking — what's there. It's actually a way of abstracting from the reality that I've been experimenting with in practice and trying to look for the real process there. And I've been doing this back and forth a few times. Because

when you go there, you can maybe generalize or abstract — first abstract and then try to operate some generalization — and then, when you have the generalization, you confront it with reality and try to predict something about the reality that you didn't observe... and then: yes, it is there. That's how I think research in general could be described: this movement of back and forth between unfolding from an observation and trying to find concepts out of this observation.

M: So the computer-mathematics of this plays two roles for me: the performance and teaching side, so that I have the computer able to feature these elements; and on the other hand, the research. There are many, many directions that I've just briefly explored.

M: One of them would be to represent your tuplet as a point in a multi-dimensional space — your space has as many dimensions as your tuplet is about. So basically, if I'm speaking of triplets, I can represent any triplet — successive three durations — as a point in three-dimensional space, with coordinates being the three durations. And then study the triplets and this groove phenomenon from this perspective. This has been one direction which is super interesting, because you suddenly look at rhythm — just because your coordinate system is oriented, you allude time. That's a question which is fun.

M: What I'm looking at is subdivision of the pulse — the pulse is a unit. So I'm looking at triplets whose sum is one. It happens that all points in three-dimensional space whose sum of coordinates equals one are comprised in one basic triangle. So it happens to be two-dimensional actually. And looking at all the possible phrasings of the triplet — if I just distinguish between longs and shorts — all the meaningful triplets can be found over just segments in this triangle. It's interesting to consider the morphing and traveling from one timbre of the pulse in triplets to another as just a travel in this triangle, generally following the axes of this triangle. Those axes are the ones that connect the very center of the triangle with one edge — that's the space you're moving in when operating those.

M: So at the end it's not a multi-dimensional space study, it's a study of those minimal figures of the dimension. The triangle is the minimal geometrical figure — you don't have a figure with two angles, so three angles is the minimum in two-dimensional space — it's about studying triangles and tetrahedra. Those figures that in each dimensional space are the minimal figures. And study within those figures symmetry and the barycenter, because the barycenter of each of those figures would be the straight tuplet. So yeah, that's one direction — the vector approach.

M: Another thing that's interesting to mention: when looking at the possible distributions of longs and shorts, you can have a theoretical tuplet that is theoretically there. For example I could phrase seven having three longs and four shorts where the four shorts are one after the other, grouped together: long long long short short short short. This is theoretically possible, but it will be very difficult for my perception to really identify this as a swinging seven. The reason is that as soon as this phrasing starts to take place, the positions of the events get really far from the expected evenly-distributed positions. A phrased seven like the one I proposed is

extremely distant from the straight seven.

M: As opposed to a well-distributed system where I'm having three longs and four shorts — maybe I start with the short and make short long short long short long short. It's symmetrical, well-distributed — I can't find a better distribution of that. That's the closest swinging seven to the straight seven template among all possible combinations of three longs and four shorts. This is another quality of your swing elements — how distant they are from the straight, how much potential energy there is because of the two points.

P: *Yeah, I just wanted to say that I read about the bell patterns of African music and this observation of the longs and shorts being mostly ideally distributed.*

M: Yeah, that's a Euclidean rhythm. Toussaint is the name of the musicologist who pointed at this. Some people know now about Euclidean rhythms. That's the same idea: given a certain number of steps, how can I best distribute a lower number of accents? There's a known algorithm for that — the Björklund algorithm. It comes from computer science, used for example to draw an oblique line on a pixelized screen: you don't have a real line, you have certain pixels going straight and then you drop, and the algorithm optimizes the distribution of those drops. Or in a lab, you have twelve positions for your chemical tubes and only seven tubes — where to place those seven tubes so that the rotation is well-balanced and you won't destroy your machine? That's the same: how to distribute seven pulses in twelve steps.

M: Now Euclidean rhythms are defined not by how close they are to the straight seven — it's just the question: what's the best distribution of, for example, 7 over 12? And there are many possible answers to that because, in that respect, a swing that is long-short — to distribute 2 over 3 — or short-long, they're both valid, they're both the best distribution. But what I'm looking at is not: what is the best distribution? It's: which distribution is actually the closest to the straight? Because it's oriented — I have an origin, which is the downbeat. So it's not about rotating.

M: So those are really three different things [demonstrating on his lap]. And it feels different in terms of groove balance etc. And it so happens that they are absolutely not equal if you look at which one is closest to the straight triplets. So this is also some research I'm doing. I'm trying to redefine this idea of Euclidean rhythm from this perspective. I want the closest to the expected straight tuplet, given that it's oriented and I have an origin — a downbeat. So I call this a Quplet, for quantized tuplet. And I am trying to find a signal-based solution that produces these Quplets rather than an algorithmic approach.

M: A Quplet will satisfy the definition of a Euclidean rhythm but not vice versa — not necessarily. And it happens that just playing with the ratios of frequencies — if you add signals corresponding to those frequencies, just by addition — you actually come to this Quplet. For example the Quplet of three over four: if I look at the peaks of a signal made of two added cosines — one being three times the frequency of the other and the other four times the frequency — the resulting signal will be cyclic with a period of one. And within that period, I look at the three highest peaks. So one fourth, two-fourths, one fourth of the period

can be attained by observing these three highest peaks when the four-signal amplitude tends to infinity. If you have a straight three-Hertz frequency signal and add a four-Hertz frequency whose amplitude tends to infinity, then the three highest peaks of that signal are going to be those selected three from the four signal — the Quplet. This is now the proof really, it works. But what's the behavior when I'm adding multiple signals etc.? So that's the whole harmonic approach — that's another direction.

P: I think we have to do round two at some point with a whiteboard and screen or over Zoom where we can show something literally. Otherwise it's probably too difficult. But it's great.

M: Yeah, there's a few more like this. I'm not really disciplined about those options of research but every now and then I come back to it and do my models and my programming and experiment.

On the naturalness of swing

P: I think one aspect I would really like to still bring out is that — if you're listening to this and you're not familiar with Malcolm's music — maybe you get the impression that it's all very theoretical and abstract. And I think it's very important to state that this is not the case, and that it's all a matter of playful exploration. And also this connection to the scientific or mathematical thing — that this whole thing is actually very natural. We were talking about triangles before, that there are basically no perfect triangles in nature. And so it's also this aspect that this rich rhythmic timbre of swinging things is actually the natural thing in a way.

M: I believe so, or at least it feels very organic. But I believe there's something natural. I've been in the French system — when you go through music education, even before you touch the instrument, you have to go through the solfège class, where you learn about the names of notes and how to count and things like that. This music theory is the first touch with music before you touch the instrument. I think this is changing luckily, but it was like this. And in that context — also because I've been sometimes replacing teachers — typically you have those kids discovering the triplet, the quarter-note triplet, and they will almost all of them go... and I think I even saw — one student once showed me a video of a quite famous cello player from the classical tradition, a great artist, giving a master class. At some point the score says a triplet and he was performing — unfortunately I don't even remember who showed me this, because this would be a great example to show, not to make fun of that person of course, but really to state that there is something that's very profound and natural.

M: I believe what's happening there — and the same with kids — is that almost always they go like 'Tri-o-le' — that's how you play triplets. You really have this displacement into long and short — why? Because your brain wants to harmonize the two. You want to bring the triplet into the two-subdivision. That's a natural thing to try to bring them together. And so it does reflect something natural. Maybe we should stop telling people: 'That's not the triplet, you're doing it wrong, it's supposed to be written like this.' But if you put a two and a three together, they have to influence each other. That's nature.

M: So of course, all these very theoretical presentations I often have may sound disconnected from reality — but for me, it really came out of first observation and physical practice. And then when looking back at practice, the abstract concepts do reflect, I believe, something that is natural, something that feels comfortable. Analog not digital. Natural in the roundness. There's a smoothness to the whole thing when it's really happening, that makes it feel organic, comfortable, natural.

On the meaning of music

P: I have one closing question — the most simple question for the end: Do you think there is some meaning in making music, or what does it mean to you?

M: Yes there's meaning in making music and it's the same meaning of basically making anything — but not quite. I think artists in the broader sense of the word — what we do is something that humans do and it's a very identifiable operation of human brains, which is to connect things. We look at reality or whatever we have in mind, we look at abstract concepts, we look. And what we do is we connect them in one way or another. And I think this is the essence — for me this is the essence of art in general and of course of music. Musicians connect pitches and tones together, painters connect shapes and colors, poets connect words, mathematicians connect mathematical concepts or formulas and so on.

M: And so this activity — to deal with binding elements of contemplation, elements of reality, to look not at the element for itself or what it is, but actually to try to make a connection between — to try to make sense of it or make fun of it or whatever it is. I think this is something that we do as humans whether we are creating this or studying these connections or actually showing the world that they exist. When we deal with connecting things, I think this is what art is about in depth.

M: And I think the profound meaning and purpose for that — socially speaking, politically speaking — is that I can be of the philosophical opinion that actually the world is connected, an infinite fabric of connections everywhere, that everything in the world is connected to everything, and so doing this art in that sense is just actually the best way to describe reality. In that respect, poetry describes reality better than any other language, because there I'm able to connect an orange and the blue moon. There is a connection because I put those two concepts or words or images together — I established the connection, maybe I don't establish, I just reveal the connection. So that's a philosophical point of view to say everything's connected and what we are doing is just showing it, making it obvious.

M: By doing that, we give access to that reality to everyone looking at what we do. And another thing is that those multiple connections — the ones that artists create — they create, they generate sense in some way, even imaginary sense. And all those connections together constitute the fabric that holds society together. This is what culture very broadly looked at is — not just artists and musicians that should be paid, but culture in general. By all the means by which we connect elements of reality, they constitute this human culture that holds society

together. So I think it's important that we do it or that some people do it if not ourselves. Because otherwise this fabric can break and this is not so good. So for me that's really the purpose of doing music — as much as doing anything, actually — I try and then enjoy working on that fabric.

P: Yeah, thank you so much. Thank you for coming here all the way!

M: Yeah, thanks for the invitation, really.

P: I'm really happy that we could do it!

M: Yeah, me too.

P: Yeah, thank you for talking today.

M: Cool.